

**URBAN GREEN SPACES IN THE CENTRAL BUSINESS DISTRICT
OF DAVAO CITY****Athena Jo A. Avila****Dr. Cherrelyn Campaña**Graduate School of Development Management –
University of Southeastern Philippines, Davao City**ABSTRACT**

This study investigates the status and assessment of identified urban green spaces (UGS) within the central business district (CBD) of Davao City. A comprehensive literature review was conducted, employing the Preferred Reporting Items Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). The findings highlight the 1-kilometer radius impact area of UGS, environmental, social and economic benefits and issues, and the challenges of UGS in Davao City. Moreover, the study supply strategies to improve the management and increase the current number of UGS to a better, healthier and sustainable communities.

Keywords:

Urban Green Spaces, urban planning, sustainability, PRISMA

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization transformed cities causes declined green cover, increased environmental stress and affect urban livability. These challenges were address in the Sustainable Development Goal 11 where the United Nations emphasized the importance of inclusive, safe, resilient and environment conscious residents (UN, 2015). Urban green spaces offered ecosystem services such as air purification, carbon sequestration, temperature regulation, stormwater management, and opportunities for recreation and psychological well-being (Gómez-Baggethun and Barton, 2013; Haase et al., 2014). These green spaces mitigate urban heat island (UHI) effect and proximity to UGS promote physical activity and mental well-being among urban residents (Elmqvist et al., 2015, Lee, 2023). However, UGS also generates ecosystem disservice like pollen allergens, proliferation of mosquitoes, root intrusion on paved jogging lanes and perimeter walls (Lyytimäki & Sipilä, 2009; Von Döhren & Haase, 2015) caused a poorly maintained park. Understanding both services promote informed decision-making and sustainable urban green space management. In the case of Davao City, one of the fastest-growing metropolitan areas in the Philippines, development pressures have led to significant transformations in land use within its Central Business District (CBD). The increasing demand for commercial, residential and infrastructure spaces has placed stress on existing green areas, potentially altering their ecological functions and accessibility (City Planning and Development Office, 2020). Despite ongoing urban greening initiatives, limited studies have systematically examined the urban green spaces services, to address this gap, learning the status, policies and management of UGS in Davao City will contribute to evidence-based urban environmental management, policy-making and sustainability.

2. METHODOLOGY**Method Used****Research Design**

The study employed descriptive research that uses spatial analysis and rigorous systematic document review. The PRISMA framework (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guided the systematic review of literature and policies. The protocol for this review has been registered in a repository such as Author, Registration ID: PRISMA-UGSDVO-2025.

Sources of Data

The study collected secondary literature for systematic review and geospatial or spatial data for site-specific analysis of Davao City's Central Business District (CBD). Academic data bases include Google Scholar, Science Direct, Scopus, and Research Gate that would provide the units of analysis or a peer-reviewed articles in the PRISMA Flow. The Satellite Imagery of Google Map provides high-resolution data, and Government documents

and maps from Davao City Planning and Development Office (CPDO), specifically the Comprehensive Land Use Plan (CLUP), and the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) for population density in the identified Barangays.

Sampling Technique

The PRISMA method guided the selection, screening, and inclusion of relevant studies. A literature sampling criterion includes studies published between 2015 to 2025 that focuses on Urban Green Spaces, Urban Greening or Parks in Davao City. Total enumeration of 150 papers was screened, then narrowed down to 18 relevant studies.

Data Gathering Instruments

The study relied on the PRISMA Flowchart that document the identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion of peer-review literature, from Google Scholars, Scopus, Google Maps, policies, ordinances and laws published in the internet. The Data Extraction Matrix a standardized table was used to record the title, author, key findings, and UGS metrics from each reviewed study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Davao City Central Business District

The primary business hub in Davao Region, Davao City serves the main trade, commerce and industry. Classified as Commercial - 3 Zone (C3-Z) it has a high-density commercial area intended for regional shopping center and other businesses that could generate traffic and require utilities and services that extend beyond local boundaries (Zoning Ordinance 2019-2028).

The Table below shows the identified urban green spaces in the central business district of Davao City within a 1-kilometer radius impact area per Barangay and estimated population count on the 2024 Philippine Statistics Authority records.

Table 1. Identified Urban Green Spaces in the Central Business District of Davao City's Impact Areas

Name of Green Space	Location	Area (Approximate)	Type	Impact Areas (Barangay)	Population Cover
People's Park	Palma Gil St.	36, 036.52 sqm	Urban Park	4A, 3A, 34D, 35D, 2A, 32D, 29C, 30C	9,860
Rizal Park	San Pedro St.	1 Ha	Civic Park	2A, 3A, 1A	6,026
Osmeña Park	San Pedro St Brgy.	5,616.48 sqm	Pocket Park	39D, 36D, 35D, 3A, 2A, 1A, 37D	17,825
Magsaysay Park	Magsaysay Ave.	33,151.16 sqm	Waterfront Park	27C, 26C, 23C, 28C, 25C, 22C, 29C, 30C	37,277
Freedom Park	Roxas Ave.	0.8 Has	Linear Park	4A, 34D, 32D, 30C	5,398
Roxas Strip Park	Roxas Ave.	0.5 Has	Recreational / Green Corridor	34D, 33D, 32D, 24C, 31D, 21C, 37D	28,549
Bucana Esplanade Davao River	Davao River, Brgy. Bucana	At least 1 km	Coastal Corridor	1A, Brgy. Bucana, 40D, 39D	36,541

The People's Park covered approximately four hectares (4 Has) had an impact to the Barangays 4A, 3A, 35D, 2A, 32D, 29C, 30C and 34D in the Davao City's CBD, significantly provided a positive environmental regulation (microclimate) which lower the local temperature, mitigating the urban heat island effect, air temperature by 1.0 to 3.5 0C (M. Amani-Beni, B. Zhang, GD Xie, and A. Jacob-Odgaard, 2021) lower than the surrounding area, and has a cooling effect nearest to the park. The park benefitted approximately 9,878 residents a population recorded

last 2024 (PSA, 2024). Among all parks, the Magsaysay Park has the highest population reach since it has an estimated total population of 37,277 from eight (8) barangays given that the park only has less than 4 hectares. Followed by Bucana Esplanade Davao River that could have 36, 541 population reach. The Davao City's Central Business District has a total of approximately 11 hectares of parks and urban green spaces against the study coverage of approximately 4.2 square kilometer or 425 hectares. These parks, serve as key recreational and ecological spaces within the identified area of the CBD.

Study Characteristic

The reviewed studies were comprised of qualitative case study and surveys, quantitative, mapping and journals. Participants were general population, affected residents, community members that provided diverse perspective on the challenges and opportunities surrounding urban green spaces. Table 1 summarizes the reviewed studies.

Table 2. Summary of Reviewed Studies

Title	Author (s)	Year	Research Design	Participants	Variables Observed	Findings	Identified Challenges
Biodiversity in the City: Fundamental Questions for Understanding the Ecology of Urban Green Spaces for Biodiversity Conservation	Lepczyk, C., Arosón, M., Evans, M., Goddard, M., Lerman, S, MacIvor, J.	2017	Qualitative	General Population	Biodiversity, Urban Green Space, Urban Ecology	Influence of UGS, connectedness, and type in the community	Urban areas expansion and urban sprawl
Public attitudes toward biodiversity-friendly greenspace management in Europe	Fischer, L et al	2019	Qualitative	2000 participants	Biodiversity, Urban Green Space, Urban Ecology	Public acceptance of biodiversity in urban green space	Tidy appearance of greenery
Associations between the perception of ecosystem services and well-being in urban parks	De Silva, CE., Bezerra, AC., Neto, CC	2023	Quantitative Regression Analysis	481 surveys	Benefits of Ecosystem Services	Willingness to pay for the benefits of services	Sustainable management of parks
Urban Green Space, Social equity and human well-being	Stewart	2025	Qualitative	General Population	Benefits of Ecosystem Services	Improved human health with UGS proximity	Limited access to parks
Urban green spaces and sustainability: Exploring the ecosystem services and disservices of grassy lawns versus floral meadows	Paudel, S., States, S.	2023	Qualitative	Literature Riview using PRISMA	Ecosystem Services and Ecosystem Disservices	Human benefits to UGS (Provisioning, Regulation and Maintenance and cultural)	Pollution, allergens and accessibility of parks and UGS

Benefits of restoring ecosystem services in urban areas	Elmqvist, T. et al	2015	Quantitative	25 urban areas	Environmental impacts of UGS	Positive environmental impact of UGS	Rapid expansion of urban cities
Urban green spaces and their impact on environmental health: a Global Review	Edeigba, BA., Ashinze, U., Umoh, AA., Biu, PW., Daraojimba, A.	2024	Qualitative	Literature Review	Effects of UGS to human Well being	Stress reduction	Preservation of Biodiversity
Does urban green space justly improve public health and well-being? A case study of Tianjin, a megacity in China	Yang, H., Chen, T., Zeng, Z., Mi F.	2022	Case Study	Residents of Tianjin	UGS Planning	Promotes urban public health	UGS layout optimization
The relation between proximity to and characteristics of green spaces to physical activity and health: a multi-dimensional sensitivity analysis in four European cities	Cardinali, M., Beenackers, M., Timmeren, A., Pottgiesser, U.	2024	Case Study	1365 participants	UGS Planning	Proximity of UGS influence physical activity	Larger radius from UGS showed negative relationship to physical activity
Urban green infrastructure in Europe: Is greenspace planning and policy compliant?	Davis, C., Laforteza, R.	2017	Qualitative	Policy Review	Urban Green Infrastructure (UGI) Planning	Interconnectedness of UGS	Lacking Policies
Davao City EO 32 Series of 2022	LGU Davao City	2022	Ordinance		Creation of Parks Management	Designating Personnel to manage and maintain parks and open spaces	Budget and Management Training

Diversity of Bird Species in Urban Green Spaces of Davao City, Mindanao, Philippines	Pingoy, B. et al	2022	Mapping		Ecosystem Services of UGS	Ecosystem services - Provisioning	Human Acts
Accessibility and use of urban green spaces and its perceived effects on the physical and mental health of the residents of Davao City	Monsad, J.,	2022	Quantitative	131 respondents	Human well-being	Positive effects of UGS in mental health	Accessibility
Urban voids in the CBD of Davao City: Their potential towards sustainable in fill development and inner urban regeneration	Magno, KW., Malaque, I.	2023	Mapping	CBD urban voids	UGS policy	Management of Urban voids that can benefit socio-economic activity	Gaps in City's urban landscape
Improving Public Parks and Developing more accessible green open spaces in Davao	IDIS	2017	Journal		Policy and Ordinance of UGS	Available urban green spaces in the city	Lack of public parks in Davao City
Visioning Accessible Green Zones	IDIS	2019	Journal		Policy and Ordinance of UGS	14.76 hectares of parks cover	1.6 M Davao City population
Davao City CLUP 2019-2028	LGU, CPDO	2019	CLUP		Maintenance of UGS, parks and open spaces	Urban Ecological Enhancement Sub-Zone (UEESZ) refers to areas intended for massive greening program	Resistance from stakeholders

Davao City CLUP 2019- 2028	LGU, CPDO	2019	CLUP		Network of Green Spaces	Develop a network of green and open spaces to minimize UHI	Resistance of affected residents
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Key findings of urban green spaces in the central business district in Davao City.

Environmental, Socio-Economic Benefits

Ecosystem Services *Provisioning* the identified UGS parks and opens serves as habitats to birds mostly observed in Peoples Park, Osmeña Park, and Magsaysay Park (Banzon, et al, 2022). *Regulating Services* include that of temperature regulation, air purification and storm water absorption and *supporting* services of nutrient cycle and water cycle. Biodiversity preservation enhances green spaces (Fischer, L et al, 2029). *Cultural Services* in the identified UGS promotes well-being and mental stability and proximity influence physical activity (Cardinali, M., Beenackers, M., Timmeren, A., Pottgiesser, U., 2024). Ecosystem services increased the customer's willingness to pay for the benefits of services (De Silva, CE., Bezerra, AC., Neto, CC, 2023). Ecosystem Disservices threaten infrastructure by root intrusion on pavements and sponge paths. It could spread pollen allergens to joggers and visitors.

Environmental Issues

Observed issues include uneven tree distribution, poor waste management, and encroachment of informal vending activities. These problems threaten the ecological integrity and intended functions of urban green spaces.

Policies, Programs and Regulations

Davao City Comprehensive Land Use Plan (CLUP) 2019-2028 integrates Urban Green Spaces as part of the city's green infrastructure creating a network of interconnected UGS in the Central Business District. Standing City Ordinance was Davao City Ecological Solid Waste Management that mitigate pollution on waste in public places and in residences. Included in the Zoning ordinance the greening activities, tree planting, park maintenance and park rehabilitation. These policies demonstrate an increasing recognition of the ecological and social roles of UGS, without disregarding the challenges in enforcement and coordination.

Challenges of Urban Green Spaces

Urban expansion hampers the benefits of UGS in the Central Business Districts; lack of policies creates a negative impact in the economic sector of the city. Constraints were limited accessibility, preservation of biodiversity, infrastructure layout and maintenance of UGS. However, Davao City's updated CLUP promotes protection and environmental balance in the CBD in the coming years.

4. CONCLUSION

The identified urban green spaces in the CBD demonstrate a well-planned and sustainable city landscapes. Assessment of these UGS gain a positive result and the people surely benefitted from. No adverse Environmental issues were identified in this study and with minimal policy gaps. These results point explicit measures like active environmental research and education, increase public acceptance of UGS policies that facilitates nature conservation (Fischer, et al, 2019).

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the conclusion, the following recommendation aims to increase the number of urban green spaces in the CBD.

1. Policy Integration. Strengthen alignment of local ordinances with national sustainability policies to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 11).
2. Participatory Management: Engage local communities and stakeholders in park maintenance initiatives and constant integration of waste management disposal.
3. Green Infrastructure Planning: Establish a network of UGS in each Barangays within the Central Business District following the directives of the Zoning Ordinance.
4. Monitoring and Evaluation: Develop a standardized assessment system for park and green space condition and usage. Design a feedback mechanism for consideration on to the next planning.
5. Public Awareness Campaigns: Promote responsible use of green spaces through education and outreach.

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